

Ratoon grain yield (t/ha)

Relationship between ratoon rating and ratoon grain yield in 22 rice cultivars. ACRI, Tamil Nadu, India, 1987 wet season.

The association between RR and ratoon yield was positive and significant (see figure). Most cultivars with high RR had high ratoon yield. RR can be used as a criterion in selecting rice cultivars for high ratooning ability. ■

Effect of leaf senescence and stubble carbohydrate content on ratoon rice yield

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We studied the relationship between carbohydrate content in the stubble and leaf senescence at main harvest and ratoon yield in rice genotypes Bhavani, MDU3, IET6262, IET6709, IET7552, and IET9235 and their crosses during Oct 1988.

Each entry was planted in two 2-m-long rows at 20- × 10-cm spacing, in a randomized block design with three replications. Recommended practices were followed for both main and ratoon crops. Ten randomly selected plants of each parent and cross from each replication were used to estimate main crop stubble carbohydrate content, leaf senescence, and ratoon yield.

Total carbohydrate content was estimated by phenol sulfuric acid method. Leaf senescence was estimated by

$$\% \text{ senescent} = \frac{\text{Total number senescent leaves}}{\text{Total number green leaves at milk stage}} \times 100$$

Relationship of carbohydrate content in stubble and leaf senescence at harvest to ratoon yield^a Madurai, India 1988.

Parent, cross	Carbohydrate content of stubble (%)	Leaf senescence (%)	Ratoon yield (g/10 plants)
Bhavani	20.5	55.2	14.4
MDU3	17.8	51.4	12.3
IET6262	21.2	57.6	12.8
IET6709	23.2	52.9	13.6
IET7552	18.8	60.8	15.1
IET9239	24.2	59.6	11.7
Bhavani/MDU3	18.6 (18.2)	54.0 (53.4)	14.5 (12.5)
Bhavani/IET6262	21.2 (19.4)	54.9 (54.2)	16.1 (13.2)
Bhavani/IET6729	20.7 (19.7)	51.2 (58.0)	15.4 (15.1)
Bhavani/IET7552	19.7 (20.9)	66.3 (58.7)	14.9 (16.3)
Bhavani/IET9239	20.6 (22.0)	55.0 (58.2)	14.3 (12.8)
MDU3/IET6262	17.6 (16.7)	52.0 (56.3)	12.8 (13.5)
MDU3/IET6709	20.2 (21.5)	51.4 (50.4)	13.1 (13.7)
MDU3/IET7552	17.8 (16.7)	51.7 (56.0)	12.4 (15.0)
MDU3/IET9239	19.4 (21.2)	56.8 (66.3)	12.5 (11.9)
IET6262/IET6709	22.0 (23.8)	58.4 (56.2)	14.4 (15.2)
IET6262/IET7552	17.5 (19.0)	62.2 (60.1)	13.0 (15.1)
IET6262/IET9239	21.7 (25.2)	52.9 (58.5)	12.8 (12.5)
IET6709/IET7552	20.7 (22.3)	56.5 (55.2)	15.2 (16.8)
IET6709/IET9239	24.8 (23.8)	52.5 (54.9)	13.5 (12.6)
IET7552/IET9239	22.6 (20.2)	62.5 (56.5)	15.9 (12.0)
Mean: Parent	20.95	56.26	13.32
cross	20.52	55.71	13.96
SE	0.43	0.94	0.28
LSD (P = 0.05)	1.22	2.65	0.78
Correlation with ratoon yield	0.0137 ^{ns}	0.2136 ^{ns}	

^aFigures in parentheses are for reciprocal cross.

IET7552 and Bhavani had the highest ratoon yields (see table). The effects of carbohydrate content of the stubble and leaf senescence at harvest on ratoon yield

were not significant, indicating low influence of these factors on ratoon yield. This emphasizes the importance of inherent ratooning ability of parents. ■

Effect of high humidity and low temperature on spikelet fertility in indica rice

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Rains, high humidity, and low temperature lower spikelet fertility in first crop indica rice and could increase percentage of empty spikelets and reduce yields. We studied the effect of such wet weather on 12 indica varieties in 1989.

Spikelet fertility percentage (SFP) was measured on 6-10 randomly selected panicles at heading. SFP was reduced with increased humidity and decreased temperature (see figure). The most important meteorological factor was relative humidity ($r = -0.96^*$), followed by mean temperature 3 d after heading.

Response of 3 groups of indica varieties to relative humidity and daily mean temperature at heading and flowering. Hangzhou, China, 1989.

Spikelet fertility percentage in indica varieties grown under different weather conditions. Hangzhou, China, 1989.

Variety	SFP at given heading date					Degree of reduction ^a (%)	Group ^b
	Normal weather	Wet weather					
	26 Jun	30 Jun	4 Jul	8 Jul	Mean		
88-7212	83.0	66.4	45.0	33.0	48.1	42.0	Susceptible
89-9382	64.9	38.5	45.7	29.7	38.0	41.5	Susceptible
89-9383	81.7	61.5	41.6	58.9	54.0	33.9	Susceptible
Cong-xie 39	87.1	74.1	54.8	50.4	59.8	31.3	Susceptible
Er-jiu-feng	87.4	66.8	65.5	56.4	62.9	28.0	Middle
HG8547	81.7	60.8	57.0	63.5	60.4	26.0	Middle
Zhen-yu 29	74.0	61.3	59.1	46.3	55.6	24.9	Middle
Ai-gan-shan-li-qi	79.2	55.2	57.2	71.2	61.2	22.7	Middle
Zhe-fu 802	85.8	75.6	55.3	70.1	67.0	21.9	Middle
Fu-lian-ai	83.6	65.3	69.2	66.6	67.0	19.8	Tolerant
6713	88.2	80.6	67.3	64.9	70.9	19.6	Tolerant
Guang-lu-ai 4	78.2	64.2	74.6	66.0	68.2	12.8	Tolerant
Mean	81.2 a	64.2 b	57.7 bc	56.4 c	59.4 bc	27.0	

^aDegree of reduction (%) = $\frac{\text{Maximum value} - \text{minimum value}}{\text{Maximum value}} \times 100$.

^bSFP degree of reduction for tolerant, intermediate, and susceptible varieties was <20, 20-30, and >30, respectively. ^cMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Among varieties, SFP differed during normal weather and wet weather (see table). The varieties could be divided into three groups according to response to wet

weather. Guang-lu-ai 4, 6713, and Fulian-ai had higher SFP in wet weather than 88-7212 and 89-9382. ■

Pest resistance—diseases

Some components of partial resistance to blast (Bl) in indica rices

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Indica rice varieties Xiang-Zhou No. 5, Er-Jiu-Feng, Zhu-Ke No. 2, and Zhe-Fu 802 have shown relatively long-lasting resistance to Bl (*Pyricularia oryzae*) in farmers' fields. In 1989, we evaluated some components of partial resistance, with Yuan-Feng-Zao as the susceptible check.

Seedlings selected for uniform growth were spray-inoculated with two pathogen isolates (10⁵ conidia/ml at 20 d after sowing). The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications of 20 seedlings each.

Incubation period (IP, time from inoculation to first appearance of lesions),

relative infection efficiency (RE, no. of lesions/plant 7 d after inoculation [DAI]), lesion size (LS, length and width of 20 randomly selected lesions from each replication, estimated in mm² [lesion length × width × 0.5]), sporulation capacity (SC, total no. of conidia produced

from 5 DAI to when a lesion stopped sporulating), and difference in infectivity (DIE, percent infected plants 7 DAI) were measured. Plants were observed every 2 h beginning 70 h after inoculation. One leaf lesion on each of 10 seedlings per variety was selected and its area measured. The leaf with lesion was placed in a glass tube containing 1 ml distilled water mixed with mercury bichloride, and left for 15 h.

Conidia samples were taken at 0800 h each day. Each glass tube was shaken vigorously to dislodge conidia and taken to the laboratory for counting. Conidia per lesion and per cm lesion area were calculated. Tubes with fresh solution were installed on the same lesions by 1700 h daily until sporulation ceased.

The partially resistant cultivars had slightly longer IP than susceptible check Yuan-Feng-Zao (see table). RIE on Xiang-Zhou No. 5, Zhe-Fu 802, and Er-Jiu-Feng were significantly less than on the susceptible check. With isolate ZC15, RIE of all test varieties was lower, indicating it is a less aggressive isolate. LS was significantly smaller on all partially resistant cultivars than on the susceptible check.

SC on all test varieties was lower than that from the susceptible check. SC on Zhu-Ke No. 2 was the lowest for both isolates.

DIE of Xiang-Zhou No. 5, Er-Jiu-Feng, and Zhu-Fu 802 were significantly lower than that of Zhu-Ke No. 2 and the susceptible check, and were much lower with isolate ZC15 (no infection on Xiang-Zhou No. 5). This indicates that isolate ZC15

The components of partial resistance of 5 rice varieties inoculated with isolates of *P. oryzae*.^a Hangzhou, China, 1989.

Variety	RIE (lesions/plant)	LS ^b (mm ²)	SC ^c		IF (h)	DIE (%)
			Per lesion	Per cm ² lesion		
<i>Race ZBIS (0262)</i>						
Xiang-Zhou No. 5	1.53 c	1.13 c	2,983 b	99,667 bc	79.2 a	46.9 b
Er-Jiu-Feng	2.36 bc	1.80 c	2,850 b	124,000 bc	73.2 c	47.1 b
Zhu-Ke No. 2	3.78 ab	2.08 b	2,038 b	70,667 c	75.9 b	81.4 a
Zhe-Fu 802	2.32 c	1.84 b	4,133 a	155,500 ab	73.0 c	51.1 b
Yuan-Feng-Zao	4.20 a	3.34 a	4,160 a	192,200 a	71.0 d	95.1 a
<i>Race ZC15 (84-76)</i>						
Xiang-Zhou No. 5	0.00	---	---	---	---	---
Er-Jiu-Feng	1.71 ab	1.54 b	5,267 a	123,000 bc	74.0 bc	26.5 c
Zhu-Ke No. 2	1.94 ab	1.49 b	2,850 b	65,667 c	83.3 a	45.1 b
Zhe-Fu 802	1.44 b	0.71 b	3,000 b	146,167 ab	77.5 b	16.9 c
Yuan-Feng-Zao	2.21 a	4.12 a	5,830 a	217,800 a	71.6 c	84.8 a

^aIn each column, variety means followed by a common later are not significantly different by DMRT at P = 0.05. ^bData from 7 DAI. ^cMean number of conidia from samples taken 5, 7, 10, and 12 DAI.